

Towards Plant Humanities: Changing Perspectives on the Botanical World in Literature

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Abstract: *Humanities, as a discipline, conventionally centers on human issues, now gesturing towards an interdisciplinary nature, has evolved to an extent where it can even encompass discourses on non-human entities like animals and plants. The development of 'Plant Humanities' as an academic field underscores the inevitability of incorporating botanical life into philosophical, cultural and ethical discourses. As an evolving interdisciplinary field, due to the flourishing of fields such as ecocriticism, environmental humanities, and plant humanities, the discourse on plant ontology dispels the anthropocentric biases through the attribution of sensitivity and agency to plant life. Theorists like Gilles Deleuze and Michael Marder offer frameworks that problematise hierarchical dualism and reimagines botanical existence beyond passive ontology. The literary representations in different genres, especially poetry as a genre offers new perceptions in tandem with the contemporary perspective on them, stressing the necessity for new ethical and intellectual considerations in the vegetal world.*

Keywords: Plant Humanities, Botany, Human-Centrism, Environment, Literature

Introduction

Going beyond the traditional anthropo-centric views, plant humanities contribute to the academic advancement of humanities, incorporating vegetal world as rich domain of philosophical, cultural and ethical enquiry. As it is an interdisciplinary field, a convergence of ecocriticism, plant studies and environmental humanities, it interrogates the idea that plants are passive and silent and introduces that the plant world possess agency, activism and sensitivity. Theorists like Deleuze, Guattari and Marder dismantle the Western metaphysics based on binaries and hierarchical structures, introducing a new mode of ontology based on rhizomatic structures. Literature, most importantly, the genre of poetry plays a crucial role in reconceptualising the vegetal world and its reciprocity with the human world. The researches in the field of plant humanities open up intellectual, aesthetic and ethical ways to reconfigure human-nonhuman reciprocity in the time of ecological challenges.

Discussion

The discipline of ‘humanities’ originally is a human-centric discourse, reviving of which is necessary as humans are alienated themselves due to the overwhelming impact of technological intrusion to human affairs. In such a juncture along with reviving human values, it extends its reach to an extent where it can even accommodate non-human categories like animals and plants. As a result of this integrated gesture, many concerned branches are incorporated into the academic field and plant humanities is such a new label which receives academic attention along with other related fields and terminologies.

According to Caroline Cornish and Mark Nesbitt: “Plant Humanities is thus an inherently interdisciplinary project, where arts and humanities researchers are often in dialogue with different ways of conceiving the relations between people and plants” (8). The interdisciplinary approach in the field has received a renewed

urgency in recent years due to the challenges ranging from climate change, food security, biodiversity loss, and so on.

The new picture is that disciplines in humanities engage in conversation with each other, like the interactions between social science and natural science, which demonstrate the interdisciplinary ambitions of the field. We recently witnessed the emergence of diverse fields in humanities such as geohumanities, animal humanities, blue humanities, critical plants studies and the like.

In the beginning, humanities included the animal discourses into its fold and as an extension, the discourse of the vegetation and plants was also annexed to it as a new domain of engagement. As Stark puts it, “while much philosophical work on the nonhuman has focused on animals, objects, forces, as well as the monstrous and the divine, it is only recently that scholarly attention in the Humanities has been directed toward plants” (180). Singer explains the reason behind the new interest in animal discourses. In his words: “Attributing ideas of agency, autonomy, percipience, and sentience to the non-human world strengthens the standing of beings— including animals and plants—historically relegated to the lower rungs of the chain of life” (Ryan 65).

In the last few years we have been attracted to vigorous debates on the position of plants in the human system, such as their cultural life and their representations in the academic and popular discourses. Human relationship with the plants has been examined from ethical, cultural, historical, textual, political and philosophical angles. The shifting attention to plant discourse in humanities happened against the backdrop of emerging interest in the discourses on nonhuman beings/entities in disciplines like animal studies, ecophilosophy and ecocriticism.

The last two decades witnessed the emergence of environmental humanities due to unprecedented scholarly interest in the field. The traditional humanities disciplines, such as geography, history, philosophy, archeology, literature and

language studies, were combined in a new interdisciplinary way. The scholars who engage in the field addressed human engagement with nature, disregarding the conventionally made Western dichotomy of nature and culture. The major conviction that led scholars to engage in the field was that it can address the existing environmental crisis, as a result, can form a new environmental awareness and ethics.

Plant humanities raise the question how “humans profoundly interact with vegetation - consuming it as food, using it as medicine, decorating their homes and cities with it, studying it, etc. While the science of ecology has long been interested in studying plants and plant communities, scholars in the environmental humanities bring the human interaction with plants into focus” (Sabine Brauckmann and Dolly Jorgensen 4). Ryan puts it explicitly, how human life is closely associated with the plant world, “Human beings breathe with plants every moment of our lives through a kind of perpetual embodied dialogue: oxygen in, carbon dioxide out” (Ryan 61). As Ryan observes, even though plants have vital importance in biosystems and human life, human-centric discourses often disregard plant-lives, their desires, and comforts. Due to its sessility, and silences, the vegetal world is often relegated/dismissed to the categories of unsensing objects and disposable things. Shedding light into the sensitivities of the plant lives, which had been subjugated and silenced human intellectual histories, new interest in plant humanities asserts an interdisciplinary approach to devise an ethics for the human interactions with the botanical world. These new ethical frameworks counterpoise the conventional anthropo-centric tendencies to present plant life as mere objects to human consumption and sensory appreciation of its beauty.

As Ryan observes, plants are highly sensitive organisms that “perceive, assess, interact and even facilitate each other’s life by actively acquiring information from their environment” (qtd. in 64). Referring to its sensitivities, he says: “in one study, mimosas (*Mimosa pudica*) ceased closing their leaves when they realized

that a recurring disturbance—in this case, being dropped—led to no actually damaging outcomes ... Such an experiment confirms the ability of plants to memorize information and coordinate behavioral responses” (Ryan 64).

Disregarding the human-centric/ anthropocentric ideas, Ryan speaks on “vegetal mode of being can accommodate the messiness of human-plant-earth-animal-biosphere-time entanglements. Such a dialectics—which collapses the binarisms of nature/culture, cause/effect, us/them”(68). This introduces an inclusive perspective which can accommodate and merge many categories which had been treated separately and prioritised one over the other. The integration of humanities and science can open up new perspectives to understand plants, transforming the existing notions on plants in art, literature, politics, and culture. Such an interdisciplinary and encompassing perspective on the botanical world is required to have a balanced and justifiable approach to the vegetal world.

The emerging works on plants not only address the relationship between humans and plants, but also what plants do to our philosophical and metaphysical systems, specifically how we deal with human and nonhuman entities in our system. In this case, the plant ontology literally troubles the existing metaphysics. Hence, this thinking about plants challenges the Western metaphysics as it invites the scholars to rethink human relation to other forms of beings. As Marder puts it, “As soon as we are willing to let go of these oppressive values, we will come to realize that from the position of absolute exteriority and heteronomy, plants accomplish a living reversal of metaphysical values, or what Derrida terms “practical deconstruction of the transcendental effect,” and thus contribute to the destabilization of hierarchical dualisms”. (55-56).

Deleuze and Guattari’s works provide great insights on plant thinking. Their metaphor/figure of rhizome which is introduced in *A Thousand Plateaus* is vegetal in every sense. The rhizome introduces a new mode of being/ontology in the world.

The rhizome introduces a conceptual pattern/structure which ensures transversal connections, and in its absence, it could have appeared as disparate things. This figure from the botanical/vegetal world provides us with new structure which can show new connections between dissimilar things. The plants can take different forms through their growth, metamorphosis and entropy through the process of taking new offshoots and forms and it is referred to as “wisdom of plants” by Deleuze and Guattari.

The resonance of Deleuzian ideas could be seen in Marder’s *Plant Thinking*. Marder explores the idea of plant thinking and how humans can participate in plant-thinking. He says that plant’s thinking is non-essential, dispersed, non-representational, and immanent. This version of thought is similar to Deleuze’s rhizomatic and dispersed thinking so that it does not appear anthropocentric in nature. Deleuze and Guattari’s ideas like the figure of the rhizome, in their model of thinking, offer us a vegetal philosophy. One of the initial contributors in the field, Marder takes a radical philosophical position in the case of plants. He observes that plants had been historically treated as passive, inert, background objects so that they were considered as lower life forms. This thinking gave humans the validity and justification for their subjection and consumption easily. Marder’s endeavor here is to challenge human conviction that plants can unreservedly be exploited for human requirements.

As Marder himself suggests, it is impossible to get complete access to the world of plants. Actually, the encounter with plants is an encounter with alterity, hence, the transactions in the plant world remain untranslatable for humans. All that we can do is engage with the edges of their being. The ethical discussions on plants also bring debates on food politics. Similar to the habit of eating meat in the West and the rest of the world, eating plants is also a habitual practice and avoidance of which is somewhat impossible. Marder’s position in this regard, as Stark puts it, is that we are not supposed to stop eating plants but we need to create a habit to “eat like a plant”.

Conventionally, in literature, plant life had been portrayed as passive and stationary being. As a result of new discourses, the question on plants' agency and complexity emerged as a topic of debate which was overlooked due to the prevailing anthropocentric perspectives. Studies in the botanical field show that rapid and targeted actions are visible in some of the plants. As white mulberry tree releases explosive pollen. New discourses in the field undermine the age-old stereotypes of the plants as static and unresponsive ontologies, demonstrating the vitality of the plant world.

Literary Treatments of Vegetal/Botanical World and Possible Plant Discourses in Humanities

The contents in literary texts and their analyses can provide new insights in the field of plant humanities. Among different literary genres, poetry is one of the effective genres which can capture plant lives in different perspectives. Poetry as a genre which enjoys the privilege of poetic license, capable of representing the vegetal interactions/ transactions better than any other genre can do. As part of analysing the treatment of plants in literary texts, we can compare and contrast the treatments of plant life as cases in Mary Colborne-Veel's poem "Song of the Trees" and Toru Dutt's "Our Casuarina Tree".

In "Song of the Trees", Mary Colborne-Veel gives agency to trees and unfolds the narrative from trees' perspective. The initial declaration in the poem – "We are the Trees" (105) -- marks a departure from human poetics and provides trees' narrative. The first stanza of the poem expresses trees' unique existence and communion with earth, sun and seasons which introduce an ontological unity of these entities transcending human experience. Lines like "Our dark and leafy glade/Bands the bright earth with softer mysteries" (105) reveal cosmological interconnections of the vegetal world. Specifically, the use of "softer mysteries"(105) indicates the mysterious relationship of trees with other elements in the universe.

The second stanza onwards, the poem deals with trees' reciprocity with humans. The tree as a speaker in the poem expresses how trees "grow for man's desire" (105), providing humans their "shelter, and food, and fire" (105) ensuring fruits and dwelling for humans. The tree is presented in the poem as a provider and humans as receivers and the trees are portrayed as companions of humans throughout their life. This idea is clear in the lines: "We are the Trees/ Who travel where he goes" (105). The line – "he wins through us" (106)-- denotes that everything that humans acquire happens through trees, as the narrative in the poem claims, even the well-built cities enormously employ wood of trees for the construction and furniture. The lines " we, his comrades still, since earth began, / Wave mournful boughs above the grave of man, And coffin his cold breast" (106) manifest the reciprocity of trees with humans from time immemorial and how trees even intervene in different phases of an individual. Thus, trees in the poem become characters who have close companionship with humans which extends even to the grave. Through these descriptions, Colborne-Veel's ideas align with Marder's 'plant thinking' and vegetal endurance which dismantle the notion of human exceptionalism, anticipating an ecological ethic in tandem with evolving ideas of plant humanities.

Toru Dutt's *Our Casuarina Tree* similarly dramatises human relationship with the botanical world. The thematic concern of the poem is the poet's childhood memories, loss of beloved ones and vitality of the casuarina tree. The tree depicted in the poem is a symbol of remembrance in which the past lingers a great amount.

The descriptions and images that Dutt provides on Casuarina tree in the poem is like that of a living entity. The poem demonstrates the magnificent and gigantic figure of the tree as a being that is surrounded by a lively ecosystem consisting of birds, bees and flowers: "The giant wears the scarf, and flowers are hung /In crimson clusters all the boughs among, / Whereon all day are gathered bird and bee"(Our Casuarina). Though the poem is distinctive for its description of its magnificence, its anthro-

centric intentions surface in the later part of the poem. The anthropocentric attitude of the poem becomes evident when the speaker says: “But not because of its magnificence/Dear is the Casuarina to my soul:/ Beneath it we have played; though years may roll,/ O sweet companions, loved with love intense,/ For your sakes, shall the tree be ever dear”(Our Casuarina). As it is clear from the lines, the tree becomes only a prop/background to showcase human relationships and emotions. These blunt anthropocentric descriptions on the tree are against the general positive attitude of the poem in its representation of the plant world.

Though in the form of a poetic exaggeration or metaphor, the poem provides the tree a mode of agency as it considers it a speaking subject. Through the description of the tree’s lament in the poem – “It is the tree’s lament, an eerie speech/, That haply to the unknown land may reach” (Our Casuarina)-- the poet attributes human emotions with the tree. The idea that aligns with the new outlook of the plant ontology in the poem is the dismantling of the conventional trend of caricaturing trees as stagnant and immobile entities, without having any qualities of living beings.

These two poems, though involving anthropocentric viewpoints and misrepresentations, showcase the importance of the literary genres in demonstrating plant thinking. Similar analyses of literary texts in different genres can demonstrate relevance of emerging academic fields like plant humanities. As evident from the analysis, the literary field can contribute a major share in advancing plant humanities as a solid academic field with more serious literary engagements in the field.

Conclusion

The evolving discourses on plant humanities demonstrate a paradigm shift in our conceptualisations of human-nonhuman reciprocity. Disregarding the anthropocentric paradigm, the domain problematises the dichotomies between nature and culture,

agency and passivity and mobility and fixity. The philosophical and theoretical engagements with the vegetal world from Deleuze's rhizomes to Marder's plant ontology provide insights on the responsive and dynamic being of them. This new insight not only redefines the plant-human exchanges but also urges for a reconsideration of their ecological responsibility and ethics. Eventually, the Plant Humanities opens up new possibilities for integrating humanistic and scientific perspectives, enabling a more inclusive and ecologically directed intellectual tradition, which can even provide a botanical framework to re-visit traditional and contemporary literary texts. This new epistemology of the botanical and vegetal world resists anthropocentric biases.

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